

It is difficult to allocate the proportional contribution of adsorption and hydrolysis towards the formation of such compounds as have been observed, viz., $K_2UO_2FeCy_6$, $xUO_2(NO_3)_2$. Experimental work on the hydrolysis and adsorption of uranyl ferrocyanide is in progress and the results will form a later communication.

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COMPOSITION OF URANYL FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES BY PHYSICO-CHEMICAL METHODS. PART II. POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF URANYL FERROCYANIDE

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The composition of uranyl ferrocyanide has been studied by potentiometric titration of uranyl nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide at several concentrations in aqueous and aq. alcoholic solutions. The composition of uranyl ferrocyanide indicated by the equivalence points corresponds to the type $K_2(UO_2)FeCy_6$, $xUO_2(NO_3)_2$. There is a good agreement between the observations by potentiometry and conductometry.

In continuation of our observations on conductometric titrations between uranyl nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide (this issue, p. 158) potentiometric titrations were carried out between the same reactants. Atanasiu (*Bull. Soc. romana, Stiinta*, 1928, 30, 69) investigated the composition of uranyl ferrocyanide by potentiometry but his conclusions were undecisive. Our observation on the composition of uranyl ferrocyanide by potentiometry is in agreement with those obtained by conductometric titrations and the results have been discussed in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analar (B.D.H.) reagents were used. Uranium in the solution of uranyl nitrate was estimated as U_2O_5 as described in part I (*loc. cit.*). The solution of potassium ferrocyanide was estimated by titrating against a standard solution of potassium permanganate.

In all the titrations potassium ferrocyanide containing 1% potassium ferricyanide was used (Kolthoff, Kolthoff and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations"). Platinum was used as an indifferent electrode (Muller, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 88, 44) which was used in conjunction with the saturated calomel electrode.

Ferri-ferrocyanide solution was dropped gradually from the burette into the solution of uranyl nitrate and the fall in E.M.F. was measured after each addition. Graphs were plotted between $E(\text{obs.})$ against the volume of ferrocyanide added. The equivalence point was found out from the steep fall in the potential indicated by the titration curves.

FIG. 1
A/1+A/10- $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$

FIG. 2
A/2- K_4FeCy_6 added to A/10- $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$

The volume corresponding to the maximum fall was taken as the point of equivalence. Titrations were done in the presence of alcohol up to 20% by volume. $M/4.855$ solution of K_4FeCy_6 would be referred as A/1 solution and $M/4.912$ solution of $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ as A/1 uranyl nitrate solution.

TABLE I

A/10- $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. = 20 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 1, curve 1).							
A/1- K_4FeCy_6 added (c.c.).	0.2	0.6	1.0	1.3	1.6	2.0	2.4
E (obs.) (volt)	0.482	0.486	0.460	0.420	0.245	0.115	0.097
A/10- $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. = 18 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 1, curve 2).							
A/1- K_4FeCy_6 added (c.c.).	0.2	0.6	0.9	1.2	1.5	1.7	2.0
E (obs.) (volt)	0.410	0.485	0.474	0.388	0.135	0.100	0.080
A/10- $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln. = 16 c.c. Alcohol = 4 c.c. (Fig. 1, curve 3)							
A/1- K_4FeCy_6 added (c.c.).	0.4	0.8	1.1	1.4	1.7	2.0	
E (obs.) (volt)	0.425	0.445	0.435	0.143	0.078	0.056	

TABLE II

A/10-UO ₂ soln. = 20 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 2, curve 1).								
A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added (c.c.)	0.4	1.6	2.2	2.8	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.4
E(obs.) (volt)	0.445	0.466	0.456	0.385	0.330	0.155	0.120	0.116
A/10-UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ soln. = 18 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 2, curve 2).								
A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added (c.c.)	0.4	1.6	2.4	3.0	3.4	4.2		
E(obs.) (volt)	0.370	0.455	0.404	0.157	0.110	0.081		
A/10-UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ soln. = 16 c.c. Alcohol = 4 c.c. (Fig. 2, curve 3).								
A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added (c.c.)	0.4	1.2	1.8	2.4	2.8	3.2		
E(obs.) (volt)	0.349	0.455	0.440	0.369	0.125	0.080		0.069

TABLE III

Tabulation of the results of the potentiometric titrations of uranyl ferrocyanide.

Theoretical value : 9.88 c.c. of M/4.855 K₄FeCy₆ ≡ 10 c.c. of M/4.912 UO₂(NO₃)₂.

A/10-UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ in the beaker (v c.c.).	Alcohol added.	K ₄ FeCy ₆ required for v c.c. of A/10-uranyl nitrate (v ₁).	K ₄ FeCy ₆ calculated for 20 c.c. of A/10-uranyl nitrate [(v ₁ /v)20].	Equiv. vol. of A/10-K ₄ FeCy ₆ [n(v ₁ /v)20].	Compound.	Curve.
A/1-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added to A/10-UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ . Conc. ratio (n) = 10:1.						
20 c.c.	0 c.c.	1.60 c.c.	1.60 c.c.	16.0 c.c.	K ₂ (UO ₂)FeCy ₆ , 0.235UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1
18	2	1.48	1.64	16.4	K ₂ (UO ₂)FeCy ₆ , 0.20UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2
16	4	1.32	1.65	16.5	K ₂ (UO ₂)FeCy ₆ , 0.197UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	3
A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added to A/10-UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ . Conc. ratio (n) = 5:1.						
20	0	3.10	3.1	15.50	K ₂ (UO ₂)FeCy ₆ , 0.274UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	1
18	2	2.8	3.11	15.55	K ₂ (UO ₂)FeCy ₆ , 0.270UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2
16	4	2.6	3.25	16.25	K ₂ (UO ₂)FeCy ₆ , 0.216UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	3

DISCUSSION

The summary of results (Table III) suggests the formation of the compound of the type K₂(UO₂)FeCy₆, xUO₂(NO₃)₂. The value of x decreases with the concentration of alcohol mixed with uranyl nitrate. The variation of the proportion of uranyl nitrate attached to the precipitated complex may be due to adsorption or hydrolysis of the precipitate or both. Since the potentiometric titration is carried out by adding ferrocyanide from the burette into uranyl nitrate taken in the beaker, the formation of adsorption complexes with uranyl nitrate is very probable. The other possibility of the formation

of molecular complex of the type $K_2(UO_2)FeCy_4, x UO_2(NO_3)_2$ may be expected from the hydrolysable character of uranyl ferrocyanide. In this case the quantity of potassium ferrocyanide required will be less than the equivalent amount as explained in the preceding paper (*loc. cit.*). The value of x in that case will be proportional to the degree of hydrolysis of uranyl ferrocyanide. It is, however, difficult to allocate the proportional contribution of adsorption and hydrolysis in modifying the composition of the adsorption complexes of uranyl ferrocyanide. Experimental work on hydrolysis and adsorption is in progress which may throw further light on the composition of such complex salts.

An interesting feature of the potentiometric titration curves of uranyl nitrate on potassium ferrocyanide is this that the potential at first rises, then falls rapidly. This rise is hardly observed in any other titration where oxidation-reduction electrode has been used.

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